

International Experience and Measures for Enhancement of Training and Fostering Quality of Educational Management Team in Vietnam

Ass. Prof, Dr. Truong Thi Bich¹, Ass. Prof, Dr. Phan Trong Ngo²

^{1,2} Researcher team of The University of Education - Hanoi National University

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 17 June 2022	From affirming the role and the requirements of educational managers (EM) during the reform period; on the basis of a brief recognition of the actual quality of education managers in the school; from some experience in fostering educational managers of Singapore and Malaysia, the article proposes measures to improve the quality of training and fostering educational managers in Vietnam: a) Increasing awareness of the role and positions of Educational Managers in the basic and comprehensive renovation of education and training; b) Fundamentally renewing the training and fostering work for Educational Managers.
Corresponding author: Truong Thi Bich	
KEYWORDS: Educational management; educational management team; the role of educational managers; training innovation and fostering of educational managers.	

I. INTRODUCTION

To improve the quality and effectiveness of education - training, management renovation is a breakthrough, pivotal and decisive step. Therefore, quality improvement of educational management team is considered as a top urgent requirement for continuous renovation of education and training innovation at the present. The document of the 11th National Party Congress also has affirmed: "To fundamentally and comprehensively renovate Vietnam's education in the direction of standardization, modernization, socialization, democratization and international integration, in which, renovating the educational management mechanism, developing the team of teachers and manager is the key step"[1].

The quality of the education management team depends on many factors, in which the program, content, manner of organization, teaching methods, etc. of training institutions, improvement of education managers are very important factors. Therefore, the investment in building up content and programs, actively renewing teaching methods, changing and diversifying forms of teaching organization, etc., of training institutions and fostering educational managers are extremely urgent.

Singapore and Malaysia, especially Singapore, are countries with a lot of experience in training and fostering school managers in general and team of principals in particular. In this article, the author focuses on the following issues: Role and requirements of educational managers in the renovation period; some basic details about the current status of quality educational managers; some international

experiences in training and fostering managers and measures to contribute to improving the quality of training and fostering educational managers in training institutions and fostering educational managers in Vietnam.

II. CONTENT

1. Role and requirements of educational managers in the renovation period

1.1. The role of the educational managers for social development

"Excellent officer will make everything perfect" and "all success or failure is based on their goodness or badness" [2]. Directive no.40-CT/TW of the Central Secretariat has affirmed: "Developing education and training is a top national policy and one of the important motivations promoting the cause of industrialization and modernization of the country, in which teachers and educational managers are the core force, playing an important role" [3].

Management capacity of managers in general and principals in particular is the ability to master a system of knowledge, skills and attitudes in management activities and to apply them appropriately in order to effectively solve the task of improving the quality of education [4].

Education managers have the role of operator of a large and complex system, and at the same time implement diverse and flexible policies to proactively address arising issues. If the previous educational managers oriented towards stability and order, the current educational managers oriented towards innovation and development.

“International Experience and Measures for Enhancement of Training and Fostering Quality of Educational Management Team in Vietnam”

With the implementation of the principle of democracy in education; today's educational managers must be politicians to create consensus among the team they manage such as guiding, counseling, facilitating, not managing by command, order or under control as before.

With the educational marketization mechanism, today's educational managers must know how to "manage like an entrepreneur" rather than just passively waiting for the allocated fixed budget.

The reason why the role of educational managers has such a radical change is also due to the characteristics of the era, of the 21st century: Globalization; internationalization; rapid development of information technology; market economy, knowledge economy and ethnic issues.

All of the above changes require education managers to be carefully and regularly prepared in terms of professional and management skills, mainly through training and improving activities for educational managers of training institutions.

1.2. Requirements on educational managers in the renovation period:

In terms of quality: Education managers must have political courage, always be consistent with the guidelines, directions and policies of the Party and State, know how to preserve, inherit and develop the intelligent and studious traditions of the nation, be always industrious, thrifty, integrity, public-spirited and selfless, etc.

In terms of capacity: Educational managers need to have the capacity to innovate their thinking; capacity for adaptation and integration; cooperation; ability to test and evaluate; mastering the Law on Education and understanding related laws; catching up summarizing and analytical skills; having compassion, honesty and humility; industrial style; decisive-minded; knowing how to apply foreign languages, IT, etc., [referred to 5]

1.3. Standards for educational managers: Along with the promulgation of Professional Standards for teachers at all levels, the Ministry of Education and Training has issued Standards designated for Educational Managers. This code includes 5 standards:

Standard 1: Political qualities and professional ethics

Standard 2: Professional and pedagogical capacity (with the following criteria: understanding the educational program, having a solid professional qualification in the subject being taught, having interdisciplinary knowledge and at least responding to grade level standards, having pedagogical capacity and ability to organize renovation of teaching and educational methods in order to have positive influence the intellectual and personality development of students, self-study and self-development of foreign language and information technology capabilities).

Standard 3: School leadership capacity (with the following criteria: analysis and forecast of strategic vision,

design and implementation, decisiveness, innovation bravery, ability to gather forces).

Standard 4: School management capacity (with the following criteria: make a plan for activities, organization structure and team development, management of teaching activities, educational and financial and school assets activities, building up an educational environment, management of administrative works, reward and commendation, management of information systems, management of examination and evaluation).

Standard 5: Capacity to build up and develop the school-family-society relationship (with the following criteria: propagating school values, coordinating with families, collaborating with the social community, cooperating and sharing of leadership experience, management and participation in social activities) [referred to 6].

With the above-mentioned 5 standards, it can be seen that the standardized requirements of educational managers are higher and broader than the standardized requirements of teachers. This standard is also an important basis for training institutions to orient, design, build and deploy appropriate and effective training and improving tasks for the educational manager at all level of education.

2. A brief overview of the quality status of educational managers at the school

Research results of some scientists on educational management in recent years have shown that the quality of educational management team has basically met the requirements and tasks, but there are still many shortcomings, specifically:

- The ability to apply foreign languages and information technology in management is still limited. Most of them have not been systematically trained on management works, their qualifications and management capacity are still restricted, and they work mainly on personal experience, so the quality and effectiveness of their work are not so high. The ability to advise, propose, direct and organize the implementation of the fields is still limited.

- There still has limitation on understanding of knowledge of the law, the organization of human resources and finance.

- Be not proactive in learning, fostering and improving professional qualifications.

- The usage and management of educational managers also have many difficulties and inadequacies: the policy regimes for teachers who have been transferred to do management work have not been satisfactorily resolved; Working conditions are still limited, so many people are not really satisfied with their work.

- The capacity and skills of managers are still inadequate: There is no overall vision in strategy formulation; educational programs, plans and schemes have not been designed in a

synchronous direction; the formulation and implementation of the educational plan at the facilities are not close to reality; professional management is still tended to administration works, no professional depth focused, guideline in the manner of movement or formality.

The main reasons for the above limitations are:

- The implementation of a number of Resolutions and Directives of the Party and some policies of the State towards education manager is still slow, lacks of drastic measures; guidelines and policies have not brought into life and capacity and quality of education managers are not fully and optimally promoted, building up a team of education manager as the core of the educational career is not enough capacity.

- Forecasting and planning of educational manager at all levels have not been paid due attention, leading to a situation of overall redundancy, lack of locality, and shortfalls between generations.

- The training and fostering work for educational manager is still tended to quantity, without much attention to quality. The curriculum, content, and methods of training and fostering are focusing on theory, not close to reality, and learners are not equipped with necessary skills for teaching and educational work. The work of training and fostering political ideology and morality for educational managers at training institutions has not been given due attention, and is sometimes overlooked or neglected. The form and duration of training and fostering are not diversified and not suitable with the actual operation of managers. The content of training and fostering has not kept pace with the innovations of general education.

- The need for training and fostering has not yet become the need of each manager. A large part of education manager participates in training courses with the need for standardization, not originated from daily work needs, not really linking training and fostering activities in schools with self-improvement of education and training in their job.

3. Experiences of Singapore and Malaysia in training and fostering educational manager.

3.1. *The philosophy and goal of fostering managers in general and principals in particular is that they have the mindset and capacity to manage change in an advanced and complex environment to become talented leaders (Singapore):* High-quality leadership ability enhances teaching activities in favor of wise direction and builds up a vision for the school in which all teachers are involved. Evidence shows that the influence of school leadership on student performance is second ranked only after teaching activities. Approximately one-quarter of the variation in student achievement is explained by school leadership [7].

3.2. *Systematically approaching the issue of training managers:* from the selection of candidates to foster managers, leaders; clear criteria must be specified, the content and methods of training must be

consistent to ensure the philosophy and the goal are achieved; while providing ongoing support for self-learning and pioneering leadership development.

3.3. *An effective performance management system is required:* Singapore's performance management system has enabled teachers and administrators to thrive up their professions and qualification. Teachers have many opportunities for professional development and to assume leadership positions on the basis of evidence of competence. Singapore's performance management system is designed in detail to be closely linked to the professional development of teachers and to provide promotion opportunities for excellent teachers. Career paths for teachers allow them to stay in the classroom and become a core teacher or a teacher who can follow a leadership path and become a leader of the nation, the territory, and the schools in the education system [7].

3.4. *Proactively recruiting and developing high-quality leadership:* Singapore has proactively selected principals from among its core teachers of leadership potential. Teachers with leadership potential are discovered early and prepared for arrangement into leadership positions, appointments are often developed from department head, vice principal, and then principal. Potential principals, who are selected after a lengthy, rigorous, intensive interview process that includes a 2-day simulated assessment, will undergo a 6-month leadership training program. This program, conducted by the Ministry of Education and Training, includes education courses, field projects, mentoring from senior and advanced principals, attached with exams of other majors and trips to other countries to learn about effective practices. One of the most important aspects of Singapore's educators development system is its investment in leadership development and support [7].

4. Some measures to improve the quality of training and fostering educational manager

As mentioned above, in this article, the author focuses on finding out and proposing some measures to improve the quality of training and fostering educational managers in training and fostering institutions. Specifically, those measures revolve around the development of training and fostering content and programs; diversify forms of teaching organization; renovate teaching methods; increase awareness and proactively train educational managers on political ideology, professional ethics, etc.

4.1. *Increase awareness of role, position of educational managers in the career of basic and comprehensive renovation of education and training:* to develop education, it is necessary to have the interplay of many factors: financial resource, human resource, physical facilities, and social support. Among such factors, teacher resource as well as

“International Experience and Measures for Enhancement of Training and Fostering Quality of Educational Management Team in Vietnam”

educational managers are irreplaceable factors, they are prerequisite for assurance of national education quality. The common goal of our country's education is to train Vietnamese people with comprehensive development of morality, knowledge, health, aesthetics and profession, to be faithful with the ideal of national independence, formulation and improvement of personality, qualities and capacity of citizen. During implementation of common goal, each level, each subject has its own suitable goals.

As analyzed, the basic functions of a manager are: Planning, organizing, leading, directing, coordinating and controlling. Managers play an important role in contributing mainly to the effectiveness and sustainable development of the group. Managers are people who work in the organization, control the work of others and **are responsible for the performance of teachers**. The strength of the school, the achievement of a collective depends a lot on the quality of the manager. In the basic and comprehensive renovation of education, the manager is the one who acquires the guidelines, policies, directives, etc., and **be active** in deployment of such guideline and policies in accordanc with characteristics and circumstances of the unit they manage. Each educational manager must be deeply aware of the important role of the position he or she assumes; dare to think, dare to do, dare to take responsibility for the work that they deploy for the unit, must be an exemplary leader in activities and in the implementation of the order and discipline of the unit.

That, bringing up awareness as well as self-perception of educational managers about their position and role in the development of the unit, on the one hand, can help educational managers be proud of the meaning of their work; On the other hand, also aware of the responsibility that they have to fulfill before their superiors. And only then, educational managers can have a serious plan in fostering and self-improvement of professional capacity, capacity of management, leadership, cultivation of political qualities, moral thinking, responding to the standards of educational managers that the Ministry of Education and Training has issued.

4.2. Fundamental innovation of training and fostering of educational managers: Training of teachers as well as educational managers must aim at supplying key human resources for the cause of fundamental and comprehensive renovation of education and training; meeting to the requirements of industrialization and modernization in the context of a socialist-oriented market economy and international integration.

It is necessary to thoroughly and comprehensively summarize the training model in training and fostering institutions, and at the same time evaluate and draw experience on a number of other training models; combine learning and training model for educational managers from countries with advanced education to build a training model

suitable to the current conditions and requirements of the country; deeply renovate training methods in the direction that educational managers know how to seek for knowledge by themselves, constantly improve moral qualities, and be able to adapt to educational practices; renovate the contents, programs and methods of training managers in a scientific way, ensuring the effectiveness and practicality, responding to the requirements of educational innovation. The fostering work must aim at encouraging self-discipline, active self-study and self-improvement, and the ability to adapt to changes in education nationwide and worldwide.

4.3. Renovate the training and fostering content and program in the direction of reducing theoretical volume and academic character; strengthening practical situations in educational management: Developing training and fostering programs is one of the tasks that need special attention. To gain effective program, it is needed to be performed on the basis of trainee's needs.

There are two levels of developing training and fostering programs for educational managers: Training programs for diplomas: bachelor, master and doctoral training programs.

Training program for certification: this can be considered as the process of updating missing or outdated knowledge, supplementing professional skills, further fostering or reinforcing professional skills for educational managers.

In Vietnam, today, there are many functional educational institutions that are tasked with fostering high-school educational managers and mainly training programs for principals, vice principals and staff planned in the network of vice-principals, but there is no program available for fostering heads of professional team. When developing a training program, it is usually based on the standards of the respective principals at all levels and standards related to school self-assessment issued by the Ministry of Education and Training. The short-term and long-term training programs focus on the following issues: *Organization and management of the school* (the organizational structure of the school apparatus related to the management board, professional units and unions in the school specified in the school's charter and regulations of the Ministry of Education and Training); *Management of the school's human resources* from managers team, teachers, staff, and students; *management of finance, facilities and equipment* serving for the school's activities; establishment of relationships between schools, families, society and educational institutions to develop school activities. In addition, there are also available with contents on *state management of education; management science and activities of inspection, assessment, and quality assurance* [8].

That shows that the training program for managers

“International Experience and Measures for Enhancement of Training and Fostering Quality of Educational Management Team in Vietnam”

and leaders in Vietnam has not focused on developing the vision and creative capacity of managers and leaders in the changing context.

In fact, the training content and program for educational managers are still lacking of its vividness, reality, and standards applied for education managers. It is necessary to mobilize experts to develop training and fostering programs for education managers who not only have academic theoretical knowledge about the science of education management, but also have knowledge, experience, and operational skills in education management in reality at schools at all levels.

The content of training and fostering programs should be regularly updated and supplemented with new knowledge in line with the development trend of the times. In fact, training and fostering programs of educational institutions are rarely updated and supplemented with information on education management science unless there is a big policy from the direction of the Ministry of Education and Training.

It is needed to build many short-term training topics for educational managers. These short-term topics will effectively supplement the insufficient scientific information on educational management for managers in a timely manner. In addition to the 3-month certificate training program, there should be seminars organized about 3 days, 5 days and should be held at the beginning of the school year or during the summer vacation. Thus, it is very suitable for managers who often have to closely follow the school's direction. Thematic content focuses on missing content or insufficient duration in the 3-month training program. The following topics are usually prioritized: Development of strategy, human resource management, financial management, evaluation in education, management decentralization, education democratization, education marketization.

Scientists and experts on educational management should research and publish books on training content in the form of handbooks on leadership skills, management skills, focusing on building common educational management situations which regularly occur in educational practice. Instructing educational management trainee to handle these situations is an effective measure for them to catch up with issue quickly and sustainably.

According to Singapore's experience, in the School Leadership and Management Program, there should be research tours of about 1 week in the ASEAN and Asia Pacific regions. The purpose is to learn from and study other education systems to provide alternative perspectives to challenge conventional thinking and ways of thinking in the current school system [9].

4.4. Renovating teaching methods: Teaching method is one of the important factors with greatly affects on the quality of training. An appropriate, scientific teaching method will create conditions for lecturers and learners to develop their full abilities in imparting, absorbing knowledge and

developing their thinking. A scientific teaching method will change the role of the teacher and at the same time create the excitement, passion and creativity of the learners.

It is a fact that in higher education institutions in general, the problem of teaching method innovation still seems to be "along behind" high school institutions. A part of university lecturers who give themselves the right to talk very beautifully about method innovation but can't practice or their practice is not so good. And of course, the way for researchers and scientists to convey knowledge to learners is still the traditional method of reading and writing.

The innovation of teaching methods of lecturers in training and fostering institutions for educational manager needs proper attention and investment. Most of the educational management trainee are managers of the Education Department, Division, principals and vice principals of schools at all levels. They are the ones who make education plan (mainly teaching and learning activities), deploy for implementation, monitor and control those activities in their units. Therefore, more than anyone else, managers must be clearly master the nature of innovation in teaching methods to make the best plan, to use teachers according to their capacity and strong points; to examine and evaluate employees in the most objective and fair way. They are also elderly learners with extensive experience in professional as well as management fields; has the ability to observe, evaluate and make high requirement on lecturers in training and fostering institutions in terms of knowledge, pedagogical style, teaching methods, and moral standards of teachers.

The nature of innovation in teaching methods is to actively engage students' activities. If, with the traditional teaching method, learning is the process of acquiring and perceiving, thereby forming knowledge, skills, ideas and emotions, then with the active teaching method, learning is the process of creating, students search for, explore, discover, practice, exploit and process information, etc., self-form their knowledge, capacity and qualities. In traditional teaching, knowledge conveyed is aiming at proving teacher's truth, while in active teaching; teachers organize cognitive activities for students and teach students how to find the truth. Regarding the organizational manner of teaching, if traditional teaching only happens within four walls, then active teaching is more flexible: learning in class, in the laboratory, on the field, in practice, Individual study, pair study, group study, whole class facing with the teacher.

Some active teaching methods need to be applied: Actively- theoretical teaching method, Problem-Based Teaching, Case-Study Teaching, Inquiry - Based Teaching, etc.

Some teaching techniques need to be applied: Teamwork, Conversation, Presentation, Brainstorming, Simulation, etc.

“International Experience and Measures for Enhancement of Training and Fostering Quality of Educational Management Team in Vietnam”

In fact, there is no single teaching method that is perfect for all situations. Each method has its own advantages and limitations, suitable for different cases in terms of subject content and characteristics, training objectives, duration, number of trainee in class, etc. Therefore, combination of all methods will bring the best fit for each subject, each lecture, and even each content in each period of lesson.

III. CONCLUSION

Management is a key factor that determines the quality of a school. In the context of educational innovation and constantly changing economic - cultural - social conditions, management team is required to acquire the capabilities and qualities to adapt to such change. Facing with a fundamental and comprehensive renovation of education, human resources, including educational managers, are the decisive factor in the quality of education. It is extremely urgent to develop measures to improve management capacity, leadership capacity, etc. for this team. Renovate the content of training and fostering programs for educational managers at institutions, innovate teaching and learning methods in a positive direction and promote the potential capacity of learners; improving the qualifications of lecturers at training and fostering institutions are measures that need full and special attention. If the above measures are implemented in a synchronous and flexible manner, the effectiveness of training and fostering for educational managers will also be significantly and surely improved; the quality of Vietnamese educational managers in the new period can be improved and integrated with regional and international education qualification.

REFERENCES

1. Communist Party of Vietnam (2011). *Documents of the 11th National Congress*.
2. *Ho Chi Minh – Complete Volume*, Volume 5 (2011). National Political Publishing House, p. 313.
3. Communist Party of Vietnam (2004). *Directive 40-CT/TW of the Course IX Secretariat Board on building and improving the quality of teachers and management officer*.
4. Ho Xuan Hong (2017). *Developing standard-based management capacity for principals of Central Highlands high school for ethnic minorities in the context of educational innovation and the 4th industrial revolution*. Summary record of the international scientific conference on development of capacity of Vietnamese educational managers in the context of 4.0 industry revolutionary, p.123-128
5. Nguyen Quoc Chi, Nguyen Thi My Loc (1996). *Management outline*. Textbook for post-graduate classes on Educational Administration, University of Pedagogy, School of Educational Managers, Hanoi.
6. Ministry of Education and Training, *Circular No. 29/2009/TT-BGDĐT dated 22nd October 2009 of the Ministry of Education and Training promulgating the Regulations on Standardization of Principals of Secondary Schools, High Schools and multi-level High Schools*.
7. Linda Darling-Hammond, Robert Rothman (2011), *Teacher and Leader Effectiveness in High- Performing Education Systems*, Alliance for Excellent Education and the Stanford Center for Opportunity Policy in Education, Washington, DC.
8. Do Thi Thuy Hang (2017). *Renovate activities of fostering educational managers of high schools in the direction of developing educational management capacity*. Summary records of the international scientific conference *Summary record of the international scientific conference on development of capacity of Vietnamese educational managers in the context of 4.0 industries revolutionary*. National Economics University Publishing House.
9. Singapore National Institute of Education (2013). *Developing School Leaders for The Nation Leadership Programmes*, Singapore.